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Luminal A breast cancers express ERBB3 and ERBB4 while Luminal B breast cancers express ERBB2.

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We conducted a genome-wide expression screen for genes required for specification or bifurcation to the luminal A and B subtypes. We report identification of the *ERBB* family growth factor receptors as likely central mediators of fate choice or lineage commitment in tumorigenesis in the human breast in vivo. Luminal A breast cancers selectively expressed receptors *ERBB3* and *ERBB4*. The data support study of dual ERBB3 and ERBB4 inhibition in luminal A breast cancer.